

A Study on the Stress Management Among College Teachers in Ramanathapuram District

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Introduction

Everyone knows what stress is, but no one can agree on a definition. Essentially, stress is the emotional and physical response you experience when you perceive an imbalance between demands placed on you and a resource at a time when coping is important. One of the difficulties about stress is that it can work for you or against you, just like a car tire. When the pressure in the tire is right, you can drive smoothly along the road: if it is too low, you feel all the bumps and the controls feel sluggish. If it is too high, you bounce over the potholes, and easily swing out of control. What this means is that you experience stress whenever you are faced with an event or situation that you perceive as challenging your ability to cope. If you see the event or situation as only mildly challenging, you will probably feel only little stress; however, if you perceive the situation or event as threatening or overwhelming your coping abilities, you will probably feel a lot of stress. Importantly, your perception of how negative an outcome could be will significantly determine what degree of stress you experience.

The Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the factors causing stress among the teachers.
2. To identify the measures taken by the organization to manage the stress in work place.
3. To study about the effects of stress on teachers in the college in Ramanathapuram district.

Research Methodology

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular subject or area of investigation backed by the data collection, compilation, presentation and interpretation of relevant details of data.

Research Design

A research design is the specification of methods and procedures for acquiring the information needed. It is the overall operational

pattern or framework of the project that stipulates what information is to be collected from which sources by what procedures. The researcher used descriptive design, which aims at portraying accurately the characteristics of a particular group or situation.

Descriptive research design, which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual, or of a group. This design concerned with specific prediction, with narration of facts and pre planned design for analysis. It is structured or well throughout in instruments for collection of data.

Sampling Method

Sampling may be defined as the selection of part of an aggregate or totality on the basis of which a judgement or inference is made about the aggregate or is made.

The researcher for this study is using Convenience Sampling and the sample size is 100 employees from various teams within the organization.

Tools of Data Collection

The questionnaire method was adopted. The questionnaire was given directly to the respondents for the collection of the data.

Sources of Data Collection

The sources of data are two types they are primary and secondary

Primary Data

It was collected from the respondents through the questionnaire

Secondary Data

It was collected from various books in library, magazines and previous records.

Analysis and Interpretations

The statistical data becomes organized, considered intelligible through classification and tabulation. It enables the analysis and interpretation. Analysis is the processing of planning the data in an ordered form in such a way to combine with the subjection of the study. And interpretation is the outcome of the analysis in the form of suggestions.

The Important Statistical Tools used in this Study are

Percentage analysis, Chi-square analysis and ANOVA

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Gender Classification of the Respondents

Table 1 Gender Classification of the Respondents

Gender	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
Female	57	57%
Male	43	43%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table one that majority of the respondents (57%) are female and only (43%) are male working in the college.

Marital Status of the Respondents

Table 2 Marital Status of the Respondents

Factor	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Married	55	55%
Un married	45	45%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 that majority of the respondents (55%) are Married, and only (45%) are Un married working in the college.

Age of the Respondents

Table 3 Age of the Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below 25 yrs	20	20%
25-30 yrs	40	40%
31-35 yrs	24	24%
Above 35 yrs	16	16%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 that majority of the respondents (40%) are 25 – 30 yrs age(24%) are 31 – 35 yrs age (20%) are below 25 yrs age and (16%) are above 35 yrs age working in the college.

Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Table 4 Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Educational Qualification	No .of respondents	Percentage
PG	50	50%
M.phil	30	30%
Ph.d	20	20%
Total	100	100%

Table 4 that majority of the respondents (50%) are PG educational Qualification (30%) are M.phil educational qualification and (20%) are Ph.D educational qualification Working in the college.

Work Experience of the Respondents

Table 5 Work Experience of the Respondents

Experience	No .of respondents	Percentage
Less than 1 year	12	12%
1 yr-3 yrs	30	30%
3yrs-4 yrs	40	40%
Above 4 yrs	18	18%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 that majority of the respondents (40%) are 3yrs 4 yrs (30%) are 1 yrs -3 yrs (18%) are above 4yrs and (12%) are less than 1year working in the college.

Monthly Income of the Respondents

Table 6 Monthly Income of the Respondents

Monthly income	No. of. respondents	Percentage
Below 10000	16	16%
10000-12000	30	30%
12000-15000	40	40%
Above 15000	14	14%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 that majority of the respondents (40%) are 12000 – 15000 monthly income (30%) are 10000 -12000 (16%) are below 10000 monthly income and (14%) are above 15000 monthly income working in the college.

Symptoms Are Affecting the Work or Performance

Table 7 Symptoms Are Affecting the Work or Performance

Factor	No .of. respondents	Percentage
Hypertension	18	18%
Tiredness	32	32%
Headaches	35	35%
Increase smoking	15	15%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 7that majority of the respondents (35%) are headaches factor (32%) are Tiredness factor (18%) are hypertension factor and (15%) are increase smoking factor working in the college.

Experience at Work Place

Table 8 Experience at Work Place

Factor	No .of. respondents	Percentage
More coffee breaks	18	18%
Over time expands	32	32%
Higher bonus	35	35%
Less meeting	15	15%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 8 that majority of the respondents (35%) are higher bonus factor (32%) are over time expands factor (18%) are more coffee breaks factor and (15%) are less meeting factor working in the college.

Opinion About the Job Security

Table 9 Opinion About the Job Security

Factor	No .of. respondents	Percentage
Highly satisfied	37	37%
Satisfied	23	23%
Neutral	28	28%
Dissatisfied	12	12%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

It is found from the table 9 that majority of the respondents (37%) are highly satisfied factor (28%) are neutral factor (23%) are satisfied factor and (12%) are dissatisfied factor working in the college

Age of the Respondents and Symptoms Affecting The Respondents

Hypothesis

H0: There is no relationship between age of the respondents and symptoms affecting the respondents.

Age	Symptoms Affect In The Respondents				Total
	Hypertension	Tiredness	Headache	Increasing Smoking	
25 Years	3	2	12	3	20
25-30	4	22	12	2	40
31-35	3	6	9	6	24
Above 35 Years	8	2	2	4	16
Total	18	32	35	15	100

Chi-square Value = 28.69
 Degrees of freedom = (C-1) (r-1)
 = (4-1) (4-1)
 = 9

The calculated value of is more than the table value. Here the hypothesis is rejected. So there is relationship between age of respondent and symptoms affecting the respondents.

Hypothesis

H0= there is no relationship between the experience of respondents and level of stress.

Experience	Level of stress			Total
	High	Medium	Low	
Less than 1 year	2	5	5	12
1-3 years	13	7	10	30
3-4 years	27	9	5	40
Above 4 years	3	3	12	18
Total	45	24	31	100

Source: Primary Data

Anova Table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	N	Mean Square	F	Table value
Between sample	14.3	4	7.15	0.0308	
Within sample	2083.02	9	231.45		3.63
Total		13			

For $V_1=4$ $V_2=9$

Therefore the table value is greater than the calculated value. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Working Conditions (VS) Level of Stress

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between working condition and level of stress.

Anova Table

Working Condition	Level of Stress			Total
	High	Medium	Low	
Highly satisfied	26	10	4	40
Satisfied	5	7	13	25
Neutral	7	4	9	20
Satisfied	7	3	5	15
Total	45	24	31	100

Source: Primary Data

Anova Table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	N	Mean Square	F	Table Value
Between sample	13.3	5	7.15	0.0308	
Within sample	2081.02	7	229.45		2.632
Total		12			

For $V_1=5$ $V_2=7$

The table value is greater than the calculated value. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore we conclude that there is no significant difference between working condition and level of stress.

Suggestions

- The management can distribute the responsibilities of the employees equally.
- Yoga and meditation programs may be conducted for the employees to decrease the stress level.
- The employees should co-operate with the management for the introduction of new changes in the college for effective result.

Conclusion

Stress in the work place has become the black plague of the present country. Much of the stress at work is caused not only by work overload and time pressure but also by lack of rewards and praise, and more importantly, by not providing individuals with the autonomy to do their work as they would like. Most of the employees were not satisfied with the grievance handling procedure of the organization which was found by the unstructured interview. Organization must begin to manage people at work differently, treating them with respect and valuing their contribution. If

the management enhance the psychological well being and health of the employees in the coming future, the organization would make more revenue as well as employee retention. Because it is said that, a healthy employee is a productive employee and mental stress is more hazardous than physical stress.

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